

Machine Learning Tools to Study Non-Globular proteins

Miriam Poley-Gil^{1*}, Nevena Ćirić^{2*}, Miguel Fernandez-Martin¹, Javier Garcia Pardo³, Rafayel Petrosyan^{4,5}, Aleksandra Gruca⁶, Marcin Grynberg⁷, Alexander M. Monzon⁸, Jovana Kovačević^{2, 9#}, R. Gonzalo Parra^{1#}

* equally contributed

#corresponding authors

1. Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC-CNS), Computational Biology Group - Plaça d'Eusebi Güell, 1-3, Les Corts, 08034 Barcelona
2. Faculty of Mathematics, University of Belgrade, Studentski trg 16, 11000 Belgrade, Serbia.
3. Institut de Biotecnologia i de Biomedicina (IBB) and Departament de Bioquímica i Biologia Molecular, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, 08193, Bellaterra, Barcelona, Spain
4. Zaven & Sonia Akian College of Science and Engineering, American University of Armenia, 0019 Yerevan, Armenia
5. L. A. Orbeli Institute of Physiology NAS RA, 0028 Yerevan, Armenia
6. Department of Computer Networks and Systems, Silesian University of Technology, Poland
7. Institute of Biochemistry and Biophysics, Polish Academy of Sciences, Pawińskiego 5a, Warsaw 02-106, Poland
8. Department of Information Engineering, University of Padova, Padova, Italy
9. Institute for Artificial Intelligence Research and Development of Serbia, Novi Sad, Serbia

Introduction:

Proteins are perhaps the most complex molecules in the biosphere. Being coded by linear polymers composed of combinations of the 20 amino acids, and in suitable conditions, proteins spontaneously and rapidly fold into well-defined three-dimensional structures. The native state of proteins is composed of a set of conformers that exist in a dynamic equilibrium, which by interacting with other proteins or small ligands, orchestrate a multitude of processes within biological systems. The majority of proteins fall into the category of globular proteins, characterised by their compact, spherical shapes that facilitate their dynamic interactions with other molecules.

However, as the structures of more and more proteins were elucidated and their biophysical properties characterised, it became apparent that nature's repertoire extends far beyond globularity. Over the years a diverse repertoire of non-globular proteins has emerged, each with its unique architecture and function(s). In this report, we review different types of non-globular proteins, describing their significance and the pivotal roles they play as key elements in molecular biology.

In the following sections, we cover aggregates, repeat proteins, metamorphic proteins, disordered proteins as well as proteins that participate in liquid-liquid phase separation (LLPS) phenomena. For each non-globular type, we review their main characteristics as well as the most relevant machine-learning-based methods to study them. To provide a comprehensive resource to the community, we have also prepared a GitHub repository where we list such methods together with their accompanying articles and code repositories: <https://github.com/nevenaciric/ML4NGP-WG3-report>

Section 1 - Protein Aggregation

Overview

Proteins are essential biomolecules in living organisms, playing critical roles in a wide range of biological functions. Their activity is finely and precisely regulated by specific intra- and intermolecular interactions, which are crucial for maintaining protein homeostasis and ensuring proper functionality¹. Within the complex and dynamic environment of cells, proteins navigate through diverse conformations, constantly seeking the lowest energy state². This energetically favourable state could correspond to a single molecule or various types of intermolecular assemblies, heavily influenced by the protein's unique nature and the specific conditions within the cellular environment. In contrast, the formation of non-native protein–protein interactions can lead to aberrant oligomerization and, ultimately, protein aggregation³. This phenomenon is of particular interest as it can result in the formation of non-structured amorphous aggregates or highly ordered amyloid fibril structures. These amyloid fibrils are notably characterized by a cross- β conformation, marking a significant shift from the protein's native conformational state^{4,5}.

Over 40 human diseases, including neurodegenerative diseases such as Alzheimer's, Parkinson's or amyotrophic lateral sclerosis, have been linked to protein misfolding and the formation of protein aggregates⁶. However, despite this association with disease, aggregation propensity is an intrinsic feature of polypeptide chains⁷. This phenomenon arises from the physicochemical necessities for forming native interactions, which unfortunately overlap with the molecular factors that drive aggregation. As a result, aggregation-prone regions (APRs) are widespread in proteins, a trait that has been conserved across proteomes for millions of years of evolution. Under this constant and inevitable pressure of aggregation, proteins have evolved to fit their solubilities to the maximum necessary to function in their natural context.

In the last few years, an important number of computational approaches have emerged as powerful tools for studying protein aggregation^{8,9}. These methods offer insights into aggregation at both the individual protein and proteome levels. Understanding protein aggregation is critical for addressing challenges in various domains, including disease pathology, evolution, protein manufacturing, nanomaterial development, and the study of functional amyloids.

In what follows, we provide a compendium of recently developed computational approaches available for predicting protein aggregation, with a special focus on ML-based methods.

Computational tools to predict protein aggregation.

We have identified over 35 prediction algorithms developed to predict protein aggregation. An important number of these tools have been specifically developed to identify aggregation-prone regions (APRs) from primary polypeptide sequences. This set of predictors can be classified into two categories, depending on whether they use experimentally or theoretically derived parameters to assess the aggregation propensity, solubility, and stability.

Over 13 aggregation predictors based on ML-based approaches have been described so far. The first set of algorithms, such as ANuPP¹⁰, Amylogram¹¹, NetCSSP¹², FiSH amyloid¹³, RF amyloid¹⁴, and Budapest¹⁵ apply ML pipelines to identify sequence-specific features and position-specific patterns, or they use energy functions of cross- β pairings. On the other hand, the most recent algorithms, such as PATH¹⁶ and CORDAX^{17,18} combine threading and machine-learning approaches to provide insights into the forces that govern the formation of amyloid assemblies by short peptides. Both tools rely on the information encoded in the crystallographic structures of amyloid steric zippers. Ultimately, they have succeeded in different applications, including protein redesign, solubility forecasting and ranking aggregation rates.

List of algorithms that use ML approaches to investigate protein aggregation many of them reviewed in ⁸

ANuPP¹⁰ (Aggregation Nucleation Prediction in Peptides and Proteins): Ensemble-classifier that identifies potential aggregation-nucleating regions trained on an experimental dataset of amyloidogenic and nonamyloidogenic hexapeptides (<https://web.iitm.ac.in/bioinfo2/ANuPP/>)

PATH¹⁶ (Prediction of Amyloidogenicity by Threading): The input sequence is threaded into templates of different structural amyloid classes and the model with the lowest energy value score according to PyRosetta is used as an input for machine learning classifiers. (<https://github.com/KubaWojciechowski/PATH>)

NetCSSP¹²: Detects non-native secondary structure propensities based on the calculation of contact-dependent secondary structure propensity (CSSP), and the search for chameleon sub-sequences using a PDB structures collection- (<http://cssp2.sookmyung.ac.kr/>)

FiSH amyloid¹³: ML method trained to recognise and classify amyloidogenic segments based on position-specific amino acid co-occurrence patterns in protein sequences.

RF Amyloid¹⁴: A random forest protein classifier based on composition and physicochemical features from protein sequences.

Budapest¹⁵: Linear Support Vector Machine (SVM)-based predictor for hexapeptides trained and tested with the experimental hexapeptide Waltz dataset. (<https://pitgroup.org/bap/>)

CORDAX^{17,18}: Logistic regression approach that detects APRs and predicts the structural topology and architecture of the fibril core. It exploits a curated amyloid template structural database generated from the WALTZ-DB 2.0 repository. (<https://cordax.switchlab.org/>)

AgMata¹⁹: Machine learning-based classifier not trained on aggregation data. It uses manually selected parameters accounting for predicted secondary structure propensities, side-chain and backbone dynamics, and a β -pairing energy function. (<https://bitbucket.org/bio2byte/agmata>)

Pre-Amyl-MLP²⁰: Machine learning-based prediction method using a multilayer perceptron-based classification that exploits a selected combination of amyloid-associated features.

AbAmyloid²¹: Random Forest classifier adopted to evaluate amino acid composition, dipeptide composition and physicochemical properties.

Pafig²² (Prediction of amyloid fibril-forming segments): Identification of amyloid fibril-prone hexapeptides with a scale derived from supervised machine learning of >500 physicochemical properties. Suitable for large-scale analysis.

APPNN²³ (Amyloidogenicity Propensity Prediction Neural Network): Machine learning approach that analyses features correlated with self-assembly of peptides and proteins into amyloids: frequency of β -sheet, isoelectric point, atom-based hydrophobic moment, helix termination parameters and ΔG° values for peptides extrapolated in 0 M urea. (<http://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/appnn/index.html>)

Amylogram¹¹: N-grams and random forest machine learning classifiers that recognise sequential patterns in the amyloids considering hydrophobicity, tendency to form β -sheets, and low flexibility of amino acid residues. (<http://smorfland.uni.wroc.pl/shiny/AmyloGram/>)

Section 2 - Repeat Proteins

Overview

Repeat proteins are commonly found across all domains of life and harbour a wide range of key roles in biological functions and processes ²⁴, from adhesion to signalling to defence mechanisms ²⁵. These proteins consist of repeated amino acid sequences that are generally not identical and are found in adjacent series. The origin of these repeats is thought to mainly derive from gene duplication events ^{26,27} resulting from slipped-strand mispairing during DNA replication ²⁸ or through replication arising during the repairing of double-strand DNA breaks ²⁹. The length of the repeating sequence unit varies considerably ^{26,27} and can be used in conjunction with their tertiary structure to group repeat proteins into five classes ^{30,31}, a classification also adopted by the RepeatsDB resource; crystalline aggregates, fibrous repeat, elongated repeat, closed repeat, beads-on-a-string ^{32,33}.

Despite their wide variation in structure and sequence, repeat proteins are identified by the short-range interactions within and between repeats ³¹. This inherent modularity is precisely what allows for the integration of multiple functions within a single domain, however, interactions between neighbouring repeats are not always conserved. Their symmetric structure challenges the standard definition of protein domains ³⁴ and thus many methods tailored to work on globular proteins need to be adapted to be applicable to repeat proteins ^{35,36}. As a consequence, many families of repeat proteins remain structurally uncharacterised by experimental methods ³⁷.

The advent of novel machine learning methods in the field of protein research opens new possibilities to deepen our understanding of these proteins that are promising candidates to be used in biotechnological and biomedical applications. Here we review some methods that have considered repeat proteins in protein design and/or modelling (*in silico* and/or experimental studies), including machine and deep learning approaches from the state-of-the-art.

Computational methods applied to the design of repeat proteins

At the turn of the century the usual form of designed repeat proteins with self-compatible repeating elements, and protein design in general, was sequence consensus-based approaches^{38,39} applied to the Ankyrin (ANK)^{40–43}, Tetratricopeptide⁴⁴, Leucine Rich (LRR)^{45–48}, Heat (Heat)⁴⁹ and Armadillo (ARM)⁵⁰ repeat containing families within the alpha-solenoid, elongated types; and the WD Repeats within the families with closed repetitive structures as well as the WW domain family⁵¹.

To date, the most extensively characterized repeat protein family is the Ankyrin Repeats Protein family or ANKs⁵². In their work, Parra et al showed that there is a significant correlation between consensus amino acid identities within the conserved positions of repeats and stability reasons for which consensus design might be successful for these proteins. Also, they found that insertions and deletions in the repetitive arrays were enriched in energetic conflicts (a.k.a highly frustrated interactions) that are supposed to be released upon binding to their partners and therefore are fundamental for function. Sequence divergence in naturally occurring proteins responds to the specific adjustments evolution has encountered to optimize the interactions of these proteins with their naturally occurring partners to the detriment of their stability. Therefore, although consensus design works to generate foldable proteins, sequence diversification from there is needed to generate functional ones. In addition, the consensus approach itself poses some inherent challenges such as: (1) the consensus sequence can differ based on the dataset's size and the method used for selecting sequences for the alignment and (2) the packing of residues, especially crucial in forming a distinctly defined hydrophobic core, isn't taken into account. Consequently, in certain cases, the consensus might exhibit suboptimal interactions between residues. Including amino acid covariation data obtained from statistical analyses of naturally occurring sequences can account for certain inter-residue coupling effects^{53–55}, however, obtaining accurate covariance estimates demands a substantial number of sequences, a resource that is not accessible to all protein families.

Deepening our understanding of the relationships between sequences, structures, dynamics and functions in repeat protein families is fundamental to fully exploiting their usefulness as amenable elements for protein design. Different computational methodologies have been developed to exploit the modular structure of repeat proteins to design specific proteins with specific functions. One example of this is the Rosetta software, an algorithm for *ab initio* protein structure prediction⁵⁶ that over the years evolved into a comprehensive package that includes programs, tools, scripts and protocols for different types of macromolecular modellings, such as ligand docking, protein-protein docking, protein design and loop modelling.

Examples of different applications of design methodologies to repeat protein architectures are shown in Table 1 (examples of entries 1-5).

Recently, novel computational methods have begun to be developed to investigate the space of folded structures that can be generated by repeating a simple structural motif in tandem, and the concept of “*de novo*” design emerges, showing that existing repeat proteins occupy only a small fraction of the possible repeat protein sequence and structure space and that it is possible to design novel repeat proteins with precisely specified geometries (Table 1, examples of entry 6-8). Since then, protein design has been about (1) structure prediction methods (the sequence is fixed and the backbone structure is unknown), (2) fixed-backbone design or inverse folding methods (the sequence is unknown but the structure is fixed) or (3) *de novo* protein design methods (neither is known): all of them are global optimization problems with the same energy function but different degrees of freedom⁵⁷. These methods are still used today, for example for the design of circular tandem repeat proteins (cTRPs)^{58,59} (Table 1, examples of entry 9-10) and knotted circular tandem repeat proteins (kcTRPs)⁶⁰ (Table 1, examples of entry 16) following a methodology proposed for closed α -solenoid repeats⁶¹ (Table 1, example of entry 7).

More recently, deep learning (DL) approaches emerged as providing a new avenue for protein design research by showing high accuracy in prediction tasks. The most obvious breakthrough came with DeepMind's AlphaFold⁶² in December 2018 in CASP13⁶³, but especially with his successor AlphaFold2⁶⁴ because of its incredible ability to accurately predict protein structures from in-silico sequences. But in parallel, also Natural Language Processing (NLP) methods were exploited to learn new protein representations by learning the language of proteins or directly generating new sequences, offering an alternative route to explicit extraction of evolutionary information from multiple sequence alignments (MSAs) by encoding protein sequence statistics without monitoring physicochemical or evolutionary relationships^{65,66} or directly generating new sequences. As a result, in just five years, the field of protein design has witnessed unparalleled advances with the consequent development of very innovative methods^{67,68}. Most of the methods within the protein design field can be classified as belonging to these classes (1) fixed-backbone design or inverse folding methods, (2) structure generation methods, (3) sequence generation methods or (4) concurrently design of sequence and structure around a scaffold. An updated and comprehensive list of DL methods for protein design can be found at https://github.com/Peldom/papers_for_protein_design_using_DL. However, not all of these developments have been tested in repeated proteins.

Recent approaches applied in repeat proteins

ProteinMPNN⁶⁹ is an efficient deep-learning-based (message-passing neural network – MPNN) algorithm for generating sequences that fold to a desired backbone or structure (inverse folding): encoder embeds the protein backbone coordinates (using PDBs as inputs), whilst the decoder outputs suitable sequences. The high rate of experimental design success of ProteinMPNN, together with the computing efficiency, applicability to almost any protein sequence design problem and lack of requirement for customization, make it broadly useful for

protein design even for repeat proteins. They found that previously suboptimal Rosetta designs of proteins that contain internal repeats could be rescued by ProteinMPNN redesign, tying the identities of proteins in equivalent positions; and in the same way, enforcing both cyclic and internal repeat symmetry by tying positions both within and between subunits. Out of the designs created by Rosetta, only 4 out of 10 that were tested turned out to be soluble, and none of them were confirmed to have the correct oligomeric state through SEC-multiangle light scattering (SEC-MALS) when expressed in *E. coli*. In contrast, among the designs generated by ProteinMPNN, 16 out of 18 were soluble, and 5 were found to have the correct oligomeric state. Of these, the design chosen for structural characterisation also showed image averages that were very consistent with the design model (Table 1, example of entry 11).

At the same time, the concept of “hallucination” was introduced ⁷⁰, inaugurating the category of concurrent design of sequence and structure. Protein hallucination works by picking random amino acid sequences where a Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) optimisation is carried out, which favours folding to a well-defined state and converges on new sequences that fold to novel structures. That means that the MCMC optimizes a random sequence through a structure prediction method (such as trRosetta or AlphaFold2) until the resulting structure fits the design goal.

The hallucination concept has been combined with sequence redesign with ProteinMPNN once target designs in cyclic oligomers are achieved ⁷¹ (Table 1, example of entry 12), given only a specification of the number of protomers and the protomer length. The resulting structures (called ‘HALs’) were topologically diverse, spanning all- α , mixed α/β , and all- β structures; and differ from the structures of cyclic de novo designs present in the PDB but also from natural proteins in both structure and sequence levels. 96 ProteinMPNN-designed HALs were tested, and found that 71/96 (74%) were expressed to high levels 50/96 (52%) had a SEC retention volume consistent with the size of the oligomer and at least 21/96 (22%) had the correct oligomeric state when assessed by SEC–multiangle light scattering (SEC-MALS). Moreover, 7/19 attempted crystallization designs were successful, all of them had the correct oligomerization state and closely matched the design models. Similarly, this approach has also been illustrated with pseudocycles in general ⁷² (Table 1, example of entry 15), this time giving structural specifications such as the number and length of the repeating units and the restriction that the repeating units close on themselves. The biophysical data of 38 structurally diverse pseudocyclic designs produced in *E. coli* were consistent with the design models, and the 3 crystal structures they were able to obtain were very close to the designed structures.

These “hallucinated” results not only demonstrated substantial efficiency both computationally and experimentally but also that a rich diversity of protein structures and assemblies is now accessible beyond what exists in the PDB. However, the need to pre-specify the scaffold structure in any way raised problems in sampling the almost unlimited number of possible protein structures for those capable of structuring a specific discontinuous functional site. This led to modifying the hallucination process in different ways such as constrained hallucination ⁷³ and RFjoint (painting) ⁷⁴ which also tried to reduce the high computational cost of gradient descent-driven hallucination approaches ⁷⁵.

On the other hand, the latest challenges in protein modelling are focusing on the application of diffusion models ⁷⁶⁻⁷⁸, attempting to overcome the complexity of protein backbone geometry and sequence-structure relationships by training a model capable of generating sequence and structure based on a set of secondary structure input constraints ⁷⁹. This approach has also been implemented in cyclic oligomers (among other symmetries), fitting the RoseTTAFold structure prediction network into a probabilistic diffusion denoising model (DDPM) ⁸⁰ (Table 1, example of entry 13).

The resulting generative model (RFdiffusion), also starting from simple molecular specifications and random noise, could correct the more minimalist descriptions of the general fold and increase design success rates. RFdiffusion allows the generation of higher-order architectures with any desired symmetry, unlike hallucination methods, which have so far been limited to cyclic symmetries. Moreover, hallucination is slow for large systems, painting fails when insufficient initial information is provided, and previous diffusion methods had low precision compared to RFdiffusion according to the authors. But most interestingly, it is considered that other equivalent structure prediction networks such as AlphaFold2 ⁶⁴, OmegaFold ⁸¹ or ESMFold ⁸² could, in principle, be also substituted in an analogous DDPM. This opens up new possibilities, especially in studies that are strongly evaluating these predictors or structure generators to discover novel and unpublished ways, as is the case of β -solenoid foldings ³⁷ (Table 1, example of entry 14).

Table 1. A non-exhaustive list of repeat protein design approaches (chronological order).

Entry	Source	Approach	Methodology	Protein families/ structures tested	Main results
1	Huang, P. S. et al., 2014⁸³	Sequence/Secondary structure-based design	Parametric backbone generation + Rosetta protein-design	Parametric bundles	Antiparallel monomeric untwisted three-helix bundle, an antiparallel monomeric right-handed four-helix bundle and a pentameric parallel left-handed five-helix bundle extremely stable were designed and successfully crystallised.
2	Voet, A. R., et al., 2014⁸⁴	Structure-based design	RosettaDock + Rosetta Fast Relax protocol	Symmetrical β -propellers	Creation and experimental validation of the first sixfold symmetrical β -propeller protein
3	Rämisch, S. et al., 2014⁸⁵	Structure-based design	Rosetta++ and Rosetta3 + RosettaScripts and RosettaRemodel	Leucine-rich repeats (LRRs)	Engineering a ring structure constructed from 10 self-compatible repeats.

			+ Angulator		
4	Parmeggiani, F. et al., 2015⁸⁶	Constraints-based design (sequence and structure information extracted from databases)	Rosetta3 de novo design + RosettaRemodel	Ankyrin (ank), armadillo (arm), tetratricopeptide repeat (TPR), HEAT, leucine-rich repeats (LRRs) and WD40)	Idealized designs generated and experimentally characterized: 80% were expressed and soluble and more than 40% were folded and monomeric with high thermal stability.
5	Park, K. et al., 2015⁸⁷	Constraints-based	RosettaCM + Rosetta Fast Relax protocol with coordinate constraints	Leucine-rich repeats (LRRs)	Design of 4 multiple-fusion constructs, all soluble and monomeric with cooperative unfolding transitions and high thermal stability. Two successfully crystallised.
6	Brunette, T. J. et al., 2015⁸⁸	De novo design (energy optimization)	RosettaRemodel + Rosetta3 + multiple independent Rosetta de novo folding trajectories	Simple helix-loop-helix structural motif	83 novel designs were experimentally characterized. 53 were monomeric and stable, 43 had solution X-ray scattering spectra consistent with the design models and the crystal structures of 15 designs spanning a broad range of curvatures were in close agreement with the design models.
7	Doyle, L. et al., 2015⁸¹	De novo design (energy optimization)	fragment assembly Rosetta ab initio protocol modified + Rosetta3 (steps: fixed-backbone sequence design and fixed-sequence structure relaxation)	α -helical toroids (closed α -solenoid repeats)	Design and validation of five crystal structures for representatives from four monomeric designed toroid families comparable to the design models
8	Huang, P. S. et al., 2016⁸⁹	De novo design (energy optimization)	RosettaRemodel	Closed TIM barrels	Experimental characterization of 33 designs
9	Correnti,	De novo	fragment	Circular	Creation and characterization of

	C.E. et al., 2020⁵⁸	design (energy optimization)	assembly Rosetta <i>ab initio</i> protocol modified + Rosetta3	tandem repeat proteins (cTRPs)	a computationally designed cTRP composed of 24 identical repeated motifs
10	Hallinan, J.P. et al., 2021⁵⁹	De novo design (energy optimization)	fragment assembly Rosetta <i>ab initio</i> protocol modified + Rosetta3	Circular tandem repeat proteins (cTRPs)	Functionalization of cTRPs with longer repeats and increased interaction surfaces: (1) a hexameric array of peptide-binding SH2 domains, and (2) a trimeric array of anti-SARS CoV-2 VHH domains
11	Dauparas, J. et al., 2022⁵⁹	De novo design (Deep Learning for Inverse Folding)	ProteinMPNN + AlphaFold2	Internal repeats	ProteinMPNN rescue of the Rosetta design made from a perfectly repeating structural and sequence unit. Residues at corresponding positions in the repeat unit were tied during ProteinMPNN sequence inference
12	Wicky, B.I. M. et al., 2022⁷¹	De novo design (Deep Learning Hallucination)	Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) + ProteinMPNN + AlphaFold2 or RoseTTAFold2	Cyclic oligomers	ProteinMPNN rescue of the first cyclic oligomers Hallucination designs made. 71/96 designs were expressed to high levels, 7/19 succeeded in solving crystal structures with the correct oligomerization state and closely matched the design models
13	Watson, J. L. et al., 2023⁸⁰	De novo design (Deep Learning Diffusion)	RoseTTAFold diffusion (RFdiffusion) + AlphaFold2 validation	Cyclic oligomers (among other symmetries)	Experimental characterization of 608 designs (closed structures TIM barrels-like, and structures with dihedral, tetrahedral and icosahedral symmetries)
14	Mesdaghi, S. et al., 2023³⁷	Deep learning for Structure Prediction	trRosetta / AlphaFold2 / RoseTTAFold	β -solenoid fold	Confirmation of a known functional link between adhesion function and the β -solenoid fold. Identification of exceptionally long and flat β -solenoid folds as possible structures of tandem repeat regions of mucins and unpublished small β -solenoid structures. Characterisation of the new β -solenoid coiled-coil shape, the Greek key FapC β -solenoid
15	An, L. et al., 2023⁷²	De novo design (Deep	Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC)	Pseudocycles (such as TIM barrels,	Biophysical data from 38 structurally diverse pseudocyclic designs are consistent with the

		Learning Hallucination)	optimization protocol + ProteinMPNN + AlphaFold2 or RoseTTAFold2	β barrels, and some helical transmembrane channels)	design models, and 3 crystal structures are very close to the designed structures
16	Doyle, L.A. et al., 2023 <small>60</small>	De novo design (energy optimization)	[fragment assembly Rosetta ab initio protocol modified + Rosetta3] (re-modified)	knotted circular Tandem Repeat Proteins (kcTRPs)	Design of proteins with trefoil (3_1) and pentafoil (5_1) knotted topologies

Section 3 - Metamorphic proteins

Overview

Most globular proteins typically adopt a singular stable structure, something that cutting-edge algorithms, such as AlphaFold2, can accurately forecast using sequence data. AlphaFold2, for instance, recognizes coevolutionary patterns in sequences that correspond to proteins with already-known structures. This approach, while effective, does pose limitations when it comes to proteins that display structural heterogeneity, such as fold-switching proteins or intrinsically disordered proteins (IDPs). However, recent computational advances open the possibility of leveraging these very same tools, originally designed for predicting the structures of monomorphous proteins, to uncover multiple structures affiliated with a single protein (structural ensemble). This ensemble of structures may arise either due to a protein's capacity to assume various conformations or the presence of extensive disordered regions within the protein that maintains stability while dynamically evolving.

AlphaFold2 is not designed to predict the structures of proteins with more than one structure⁹⁰. That is, some proteins have two or more stable three-dimensional states, these states might change from one to another due to an outside alteration or might coexist in a dynamic equilibrium. AlphaFold2 predicts structure from sequence by detecting coevolutionary patterns in sequence identities. It can do it because it has been trained in the universe of known structures (PDB). However, when given a fold-switching protein it fails to predict all possible structures this sequence might adopt in a natural setting. The main reason behind this is the fact that most of the PDB records are single-fold proteins, and therefore, the algorithm has been trained to predict one structure for each sequence. Even when provided with the sequence of a PDB-reported fold-switching protein, it only predicts one of the multiple structures associated with that sequence in the PDB. Curiously, these fold-switching regions are very confidently predicted (high pLDDT values), suggesting that there is an observable evolutionary conservation in these regions that could be exploited for their detection.

Recent approaches applied to metamorphic proteins

Alternative Contact Enhancer (ACE) ⁹¹ is an algorithm trained with protein superfamilies containing fold-switching and single-fold proteins, as well as protein subfamilies where fold-switching proteins are overrepresented to detect coevolutionary signals unique to these fold-switching regions, also known as dual-fold coevolution. The sequence corresponding to a fold-switching protein is used to generate a deep MSA, which is pruned repeatedly to generate successively shallower MSAs with sequences increasingly identical to the query. These subfamily-specific MSAs unmask coevolutionary couplings from alternative conformations. GREMLIN ^{92,93} and MSA Transformer ⁹⁴ are used for the coevolutionary analysis and both method's results are superimposed on a single contact map, discovering unobserved contacts (not overlapping with any experimentally determined contact) that might be alternative conformations or folding intermediates.

available at: https://github.com/ncbi/dual_fold_coevolution.

Cfold ⁹⁵ is a machine-learning tool designed for the prediction of all protein conformations in **monomeric proteins**. Cfold's architecture is almost a complete copy of AlphaFold2, but the template track is removed from the structure prediction step, focusing on the MSAs and therefore predicting new structures instead of emulating existing ones from the PDB. A conformational split of structural clusters is created from the PDB. Then, a CNN, adapted from Evoformer (AlphaFold2 CNN) predicts alternative protein conformations from the MSAs by creating many coevolutionary representations for the same protein.

Also, the training set is composed of structural clusters of sequences, enabling a more refined mapping of sequences to an exact protein conformation.

available for local installation at: <https://github.com/patrickbryant1/Cfold>

Google collab notebook available at:

<https://colab.research.google.com/github/patrickbryant1/Cfold/blob/master/Cfold.ipynb>

AlphaFold Cluster ⁹⁶ is a method developed by DeepMind that combines sequence clustering and the AlphaFold2 model to predict protein structures. The AlphaFold2 model takes a protein sequence as input and uses multiple sequence alignment (MSA) statistics to generate a protein-specific potential surface. AlphaFold-Cluster extends this approach by introducing sequence clustering. The hypothesis suggests that different states of metamorphic proteins share different coevolutionary signals. Using DBSCAN, a density-based non-parametric clustering algorithm, the initial MSA is divided into different sub-MSAs that share some coevolutionary signal. Each of these sub-MSAs is imputed separately into AF2, which will predict a different structure for each of them, effectively sampling the alternate conformations of a metamorphic protein.

available at: https://github.com/HWaymentSteele/AF_Cluster

Section 4 - Intrinsically Disordered Proteins (IDPs)

Overview

In contrast to most globular proteins and metamorphic proteins that interconvert between a few stable conformers, not all proteins can attain a stable conformation. Approximately, one-third of the human proteome contains intrinsically disordered regions that comprise at least 40% of their length, resulting in many different possible structures these regions can adopt. The heterogeneous and dynamic nature of these proteins makes it difficult for tools like AF2 to predict one single structure associated with it. Therefore, tools that can predict multiple conformations that represent the dynamic ensembles of IDPs and highly flexible proteins are desired. In this section, we will cover tools to explore and reproduce IDPs conformational ensembles as well as tools to detect disordered regions in IDPs.

Section 4A - Methods to study IDPs Conformational Ensembles

AlphaFold tends to assign very low pLDDT values to disordered regions (IDR structure not accurately predicted). However, if there is an evolutionary pattern in these regions, AF2 should be able to find them, provided that is used properly ⁹⁷. By using the already calculated inter-residue distances in a protein (disordered or not), the different structures of the **ensemble of structures** AF2 predicts can be **reweighted** so that all of them are compliant with the **inter-residue distances**, which are treated as structural restraints. Effectively, they describe a way to use AlphaFold (trained to predict single-folded proteins) to create structural ensembles that represent the native state of an intrinsically disordered protein (IDP).

No code available: the authors do describe how to perform the reweighting process in the Methods section.

Principal Component Analysis (PCA), Neural Network (NN) and Support-Vector-Machine (SVM) algorithms were trained to predict whether an IDP will aggregate or not ⁹⁸. These 3 machine-learning methods were combined with 49 predictors (most of which were scores from other machine-learning algorithms) to predict whether an IDP will enter into detergent-insoluble or detergent-soluble aggregates.

CALVADOS ⁹⁹ is a machine-learning model that generates conformational ensembles of IDRs from sequence only. Using AlphaFold's low pLDDT values, the disorder was predicted to find IDRs in the human proteome. CALVADOS is a coarse-grained model that accurately predicts the conformational properties and propensity to undergo phase separation for IDPs. Using CALVADOS, MD simulations were performed to generate conformational ensembles.

The main application of the CALVADOS model is to predict the chain compaction and phase-separation propensity.

available for local installation at: github.com/KULL-Centre/CALVADOS

available to run in Google Colab at: github.com/KULL-Centre/EnsembleLab

Section 4B - Methods for IDPs Detection

Overview

Intrinsically disordered proteins (IDPs) and regions (IDRs) are widely distributed within most proteomes, and are associated with many essential biological processes as well as a broad range of human diseases¹⁰⁰. Given the prevalence of intrinsic disorder and the growing acknowledgement of the functional relevance of these proteins/regions, considerable effort has been made by the bioinformatics community to provide tools to predict protein disorder. To date, based on various physicochemical characteristics of protein disorder and its differences compared to ordered structures, along with a variety of diverse computational approaches, numerous disorder predictors have been developed.

[Here](#), we present an overview of 16 protein disorder prediction methods, most of which are recently developed and ML-based, including a thorough analysis of the biological principles and computational approaches they are based on. Regarding this, we precisely describe the methodology used for building the models and categorize them by different classification schemes. The performance of these models is presented by their scores from the most recent CAID competition¹⁰¹.

Most broadly, disorder prediction methods can be classified into four main categories: (1) *ab initio*, or sequence only, (2) clustering, (3) template or homology-based and (4) meta or consensus¹⁰¹. There are also methods that combine two or more of these approaches - those are categorized as hybrid methods. Each of these approaches results in different characteristics of the model, such as precision of the predicted disordered region boundaries, sizes of individual predicted disordered regions (in terms of suitability of the model for predicting longer or shorter disorder regions), different execution speeds due to drawing information from multiple sources such as tertiary structure predicted models (clustering methods), homologous structure templates (template/homology-based methods) or output from other disorder predictors (meta/consensus methods).

According to another type of classification scheme, based on their methodologies disorder prediction methods can be divided into four categories, including physicochemical-based method, machine-learning-based method, template-based method and meta-methods¹⁰². We address this by precisely describing the methodology used for building the model.

Another important characteristic of the models that affects their execution speed is the use of protein's evolutionary information because models that generate multiple sequence alignment

(or use it indirectly by relying on some other predictor that requires sequence evolutionary information) are much slower and are therefore not suitable for large-scale proteome-wide prediction. Regarding this, we indicate for each of the listed models whether they rely on protein's evolutionary information or not.

An additional contribution of this work is the models' retraining availability analysis. We describe in detail the predictors' implementation source code (if available) and propose an alternative way of overcoming the obstacles with a retraining procedure (if possible). This insight might be very useful, since older models were trained on significantly smaller datasets compared to the newer ones, due to the increase in the number of experimentally annotated disorder proteins with time. Concerning this, we discuss in detail the possibility of retraining the models on a different (bigger, novel) dataset to perform a full-scale comparison of their expression power in delineating disorders in proteins. Unfortunately, it turns out that most of the predictors either cannot be retrained, or they can but it cannot be easily done.

Summary

Following table shows the summary statistics of the different disorder predictor characteristics. Firstly, almost all of the models are based on the ab initio approach and there is a noticeable shortage of novel methods that predict disorder-binding regions. Regarding the methodology, in the last period, there has been a notable prevailing trend of machine-learning-based methods, especially the ones that utilize deep neural networks. There have been tried out vast variety of different types of machine learning models, starting from the most simple ones (by construction, not by expression power), such as logistic regression, SVM and KNN, all the way to the deep neural networks with very complex architectures, including the most recent and groundbreaking techniques for designing the neural network architecture, such as the Squeeze-and-Excitation attention mechanism and residual connections between different hidden layers of the neural network. Further, roughly half of the listed methods rely on protein's evolutionary information and half of them do not. And, as for the possibility of retraining the models, unfortunately, it turns out that many of the predictors either cannot be retrained, or they can but it cannot be easily done (only with an implementation from scratch).

Type of prediction*	Method category	Relying on sequence evolutionary information	Form of model availability*
DP - 11 BA - 0 DP & BA - 5	ab initio - 11 clustering - 0 template - 0 meta - 1 hybrid - 4	Yes - 11 No - 5	WS & SP - 10 SP - 4 N/A - 2

Table 1: Summary statistics of the different disorder predictor characteristics. Type of prediction: *DP* – disorder propensity, *BA* – binding affinity predictions. Availability: *SP* – standalone program, *WS* – web server, *N/A* – not available.

Models implementation description

The [AUCpred](#) model ¹⁰³ employs a new machine learning method called Deep Convolutional Neural Fields (DeepCNF) to obtain protein's IDR predictions. *DeepCNF* - an integration of CRF (Conditional Random Fields) and DCNN (Deep Convolutional Neural Network). DeepCNF can also be viewed as CRF with DCNN as its non-linear feature-generating function. It can model not only complex sequence-structure relationships in a hierarchical manner (DCNN) but also correlation among adjacent residues (CRF). To deal with a highly imbalanced order/disorder ratio, instead of training DeepCNF by widely used maximum likelihood, a new approach was developed that maximizes the AUC score, which is an unbiased measure for class-imbalanced data. **There is a variant of the model that uses only (primary) sequence-related features and a variant that uses sequence-related features (primary sequence, physicochemical properties of each AA, etc.), evolution-related (sequence profile) and structure-level (predicted secondary structure and solvent accessibility) features.**

The [fIDPnn](#) model ¹⁰⁴ consists of two modules - one for predicting disorder regions and the other for the function prediction of the disordered regions generated by the first module. This way the function prediction lines up with and complements the disorder functions, i.e. function predictions cannot be misaligned with the outputs of the disorder predictor module (as is the case with other models where these two tasks are decoupled). The model generates putative functions for the predicted IDRs covering the four most commonly annotated functions: protein-binding, DNA-binding, RNA-binding and linkers (protein regions that serve as linkers/spacers in multi-domain proteins or between structured constituents in domains, in single-domain proteins). **There is a variant of the model that uses a simple logistic regression model for the disorder prediction and a random forest for the function prediction and a variant that uses a deep feedforward neural network for the disorder prediction and a random forest for the function prediction.** The model relies on the predictions of other models (IUPred, PSIPRED, DisoRDPbind, DFLpred and fMoRFpred) taking their outputs as its features.

[DisoMine](#) ¹⁰⁵ is implemented as a Recurrent Neural Network (RNN). The network is composed of two submodules - the first one consists of a 2-layer Bidirectional Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU) network and the second one is a Feed Forward Neural Network (FFNN) using a 11-neurons sliding window. The main advantage of using a RNN is that it takes into consideration the complete full-length protein, resulting in a more comprehensive prediction. The bidirectional approach ensures that one sequence direction is not preferred over the other when analyzing the protein sequence. The output of the BiGRU is then passed to a FFNN sub-module using a 11-neuron sliding window to leverage the importance of the local context. The model relies on the predictions of other models (PSIPRED, DynaMine and EFoldMine) taking their outputs as its features.

[PreDisorder](#) ¹⁰⁶ is a web server based on *ab initio* method that participated in CASP8 under the group name MULTICOM_CMFR. It is a 1D Recursive Neural Network which takes as input the predicted secondary structure, solvent accessibility and template profile generated using PSI-BLAST for a given protein sequence. More specifically, for each protein sequence, the input is a 1D array I whose length is equal to the total number of residues in the sequence. Each

element lk is a vector with 25 values which represent the residue k . Of these 25 values, 20 represent the frequencies of each AA at the corresponding position from the PSI-BLAST profile and the other 5 are binary values used to encode the predicted secondary structure (Helix, Strand and Coil) and solvent accessibility of the residue.

[rawMSA](#) methodology¹⁰⁷ introduces a new system for *de novo* prediction of structural properties of proteins which exploits the capability of Deep Neural Networks to automatically extract relevant features from the raw data. The core idea is using raw Multiple Sequence Alignments (MSA) of proteins as input instead of compressing them into protein sequence profiles (PSSM), as is common practice. The embedding technique was used to map each residue character in the MSA into a n -dimensional vector of floats. This way of representing residues is adaptively learned by the network based on the context, i.e. the structural property of importance.

The [SPOT-Disorder1](#) method¹⁰⁸ represents the first application of a Long Short Term Memory (LSTM) network in protein disorder prediction. It combines LSTM with Deep Bidirectional Recurrent Neural Networks for capturing long-range (non-local) interactions between amino acid residues that are structural but not sequence neighbours. Input features include evolutionary, predicted local structure properties (solvent accessibility, number of neighbouring residues in 3D-structure and secondary structure properties) and physicochemical properties for each amino acid at its position in the polypeptide chain. A version of a SPOT-Disorder1 model that also predicts disorder binding regions relies on the assumption that semi-disorder (defined as predicted disorder probability around 0.5) is implicated in induced folding and protein aggregation (by binding with other proteins). The primary model is extended by adding two parameters for defining a semi-disorder region (region enclosing a predicted disorder probability of 0.5).

[SPOT-Disorder2](#) model¹⁰⁹ is an ensemble of hybrid neural network models consisting of both LSTM Bidirectional Recurrent Neural Networks (LSTM-BRNNs) and Residual Convolutional Neural Networks (ResNets) that incorporate Inception paths and Squeeze-and-Excitation attention mechanism (IncReSeNets). This architecture of network ensemble is advantageous because it can congregate and propagate both short-distance (IncReSeNet) and long-distance (LSTM-BRNN) interactions through the protein sequence, while the use of an ensemble contributes to increasing accuracy through the removal of spurious false predictions. A large corpus of networks with various architectures was examined and the 5 top-performing models are used in the final ensemble for SPOT-Disorder2. The model employed a similar set of features to [SPOT-Disorder1](#). Besides the PSSM profile, evolutionary features also included the Hidden Markov Models (HMM) profiles obtained from HHblits. Also, for prediction of local structure properties instead of [SPIDER2](#) it was utilized [SPOT-1D](#) which is the latest state-of-the-art predictor for this purpose. As well as SPOT-Disorder1, with minor extensions model can be adapted to predict disorder-binding regions.

[SPOT-Disorder-Single](#)¹¹⁰ is a single-sequence-based method for predicting intrinsic disorder. It is an ensemble of 9 models each consisting of ResNets and/or LSTM-BRNNs (1 LSTM-BRNN

model, 1 ResNet-LSTM-BRNN model and 7 LSTM-BNN-ResNet model, naming according to the order of combining these two types of NNs). Although Bidirectional LSTM models by themselves provide high-accuracy disorder prediction, their combination with Residual CNNs increases the effectiveness in propagating information through the protein sequence. Furthermore, putting these models in an ensemble provides a more general output due to the suppression of spurious generalizations made after progressing through the unique learning path of each model. Unlike [SPOT-Disorder1](#) (authors' previous model), SPOT-Disorder-Single predicts intrinsic disorder of proteins by using the sequence of amino acids only, i.e. its input feature vector is the one-hot encoded protein sequence.

[DISOPRED3](#)¹¹¹ is the third version of the DISOPRED model which extends its predecessors with new modules for disorder prediction and an integrative (meta) approach to combine their outputs to obtain the final prediction, along with a new module to predict protein-binding sites within putative disordered regions. The architecture of the model consists of 3 first-level component predictors - [DISOPRED2](#)¹¹² SVM, the original FFNN ([DISOPRED1](#)¹¹³) but trained on a novel dataset rich with long disordered regions, and a pristinely new KNN predictor. A small second-stage neural network was then trained to combine the three component predictors' outputs into a single prediction output. On top of that, to determine residues which might be part of protein-binding sites a novel SVM based classifier was employed. The input for disorder prediction modules of the model is the PSSM profile alone, while the binding sites module takes additional sequence-derived features i.e. positional information and amino acid composition of the (disordered) input region.

[DisEMBL](#)¹¹⁴ is a method for the prediction of protein disorders based on different criteria for defining disorders. **DisEMBL-465** is a version of this model that treats protein disorder as missing coordinates in X-ray structures as defined by REMARK 465 entries in the PDB database. According to this criteria, the residues' labels are assigned on the corresponding protein dataset. This version of the model utilizes an ensemble of 5 Feed Forward Neural Networks, each with one hidden layer. **DisEMBL-HL** is a version of this model that treats protein disorder as so-called 'Hot Loops' i.e. the loops (secondary structure elements) with a high degree of mobility as determined from the X-ray structures' temperature factors (B factors). According to this criteria, the residues' labels are assigned on the corresponding protein dataset. This version of the model utilizes a composition of two Feed Forward Neural Networks ensembles - one for filtering 'loop' regions from 'non-loop' regions of the protein (non-loop regions are immediately declared as ordered), and the other for asserting the 'hot loops' and 'non-hot loops' regions.

[DFLpred](#)¹¹⁵ is a first-of-its-kind sequence-based predictor for disordered flexible linkers (DFLs). It is a logistic regression-based model that combines empirically selected features which comprise physicochemical properties of residues (according to [AAindex](#) database¹¹⁶) and sequence-derived predictions generated with [IUPred](#)¹¹⁷ model. These features were selected by a two-step procedure that eliminates low predictive features i.e. features that have low correlation with the annotation of the DFLs (quantified with point-biserial and ϕ correlation coefficients), as well as mutually correlated features (quantified with Pearson correlation

coefficient). Four features were selected and those are the structured domains and long disordered regions annotations generated respectively with IUPred-struct and IUPred-long predictors, and two physicochemical properties of residues that quantify propensity for formation of helices and turns (secondary structure elements). The per-residue feature vector for the logistic regression model is computed using a sliding window technique which aggregates previously selected features on sequential neighborhoods of the residue.

[DisPredict2](#)¹¹⁸ is an enhanced disorder predictor that incorporates a new position-specific residual feature, namely PSEE, into the feature set of the author's previous disorder predictor [DisPredict](#). A novel feature estimates the position-specific estimated energy (PSEE) contribution of each residue to the total free energy of a protein. The quantification of PSEE is based on the interaction energies of the target residue with potential contact partners (residues) in its neighbourhood along the sequence, as well as the relative exposure of the target residue and its partners. It considers the interaction effect of the target residue in terms of pairwise contact energies between the target residue and its contact partners of different amino acid types, which are estimated from the protein's primary sequence alone (by energy predictor matrix from [IUPred](#)), unlike the usually used energy functions which require the known three-dimensional structure of a protein. Furthermore, it utilizes the predicted relative exposure (or burial) of a residue to approximate the local three-dimensional conformational position and stability of the residue. The accessible surface area (ASA) predicted by [REGAd3p](#)¹¹⁹ is used to determine residues' relative exposure. Besides PSEE, DisPredict2 includes 56 features per residue used in the previous version of the model. Those features include amino acid type, different physicochemical properties of residues, predicted secondary structure with [SPINE-X](#)¹²⁰, evolutionary information in the form of the position-specific scoring matrix (PSSM), et al. Before feeding these features into the SVM classifier sliding window technique is applied to aggregate the residues' neighboring information.

[MobiDB-lite](#)¹²¹ is a meta-predictor that combines 8 state-of-the-art disorder predictors - three variants of ESpritz (ESpritz DisProt, ESpritz NMR, ESpritz Xray), two variants of IUPred (IUPred-long, IUPred-short), DisEMBL and GlobPlot. Their raw disorder predictions are combined into a consensus using a threshold of at least 5 out of 8 predictors to define a residue as disordered. To increase its robustness, the consensus is refined by an iterative filtering step to remove spurious short regions of disorder inside order and vice-versa, ensuring that predicted regions cover at least 20 consecutive residues. Therefore, MobiDB-light predictions are highly specific (i.e. few false positives), preferring to predict fewer but longer disorder stretches.

Section 5 - Liquid-Liquid Phase Separation (LLPS)

Overview:

The phenomenon of liquid-liquid phase separation (LLPS) plays a pivotal role in the formation of membraneless organelles, also referred to as biomolecular condensates or droplets. The involvement of LLPS in various age-related diseases has stimulated a significant surge in

biomedical research and biology, leveraging a combination of experimental and computational approaches to unravel this complex process. Over recent years, multiple computational tools, including databases, predictors, and simulations, have been developed to identify and characterize the proteins responsible for driving LLPS and forming condensates. Non-globular proteins, particularly IDPs, low complexity regions and tandem repeat proteins, play a fundamental role in driving and regulating the condensate formation. This report aims to provide an overview of the cutting-edge computational resources in the field of LLPS, emphasizing their significance, applications, and upcoming challenges in this domain.

Methods to study LLPS:

PSPer

PSPer¹²² is a method trained to identify prion-like RNA binding phase-separation proteins (PSPs). This method is focused on a particular feature of LLPS proteins and provides an overall score for a given protein depending on the presence of this feature. The method is trained on an experimental dataset of FUS-like PSPs, and the biophysical characteristics (PLD and RNA binding domain, RNA-recognition motif, disordered and additional domains) that belong to each region, implemented in a probabilistic model. This method was also trained including a negative dataset of ordered proteins, so it is expected that its performance is increased on those disordered proteins driven LLPS. <http://bio2byte.com/psp/>

PLAAC

PLAAC¹²³ predicts prion-like amino acid composition, usually enriched in polar-residues by using Hidden Markov Model (HMM). This method was originally developed before realizing the implication of PLDs in LLPS, and consequently it is not trained to identify the majority of phase separating regions. <http://plaac.wi.mit.edu/>

PScore

PScore¹²⁴ is a statistical scoring algorithm that predicts pi-pi interactions. It compares pi-pi interactions predicted in the target proteins with all proteins found in the PDB to assign a score of phase-separation propensity. <http://abragam.med.utoronto.ca/~JFKlab/Software/psp.htm>

catGRANULE

catGRANULE¹²⁵ is a method that was originally trained against yeast protein but it has been shown to be useful to predict human phase-separating proteins (10). The algorithm is based on sequence composition statistics to differentiate proteins that are localized in yeast granules from the rest of the yeast proteome. The features considered to weight the residues are disorder and nucleic-acid binding propensities, as well as properties of some amino acids. http://s.tartaglialab.com/new_submission/catGRANULES

PSPredictor

PSPredictor¹²⁶ is a machine learning approach to predict proteins that phase separately, trained on a set of experimentally validated protein sequences in the LLPSDB database. <http://www.pkumdl.cn:8000/PSPredictor/>

PSAP

PSAP ¹²⁷ is a random forest classifier to predict the probability of proteins to mediate phase separation. This classifier is trained on a set of 90 high-confident HUMAN proteins that drive LLPS. <https://github.com/vanheeringen-lab/psap>

FuzDrop

FuzDrop ¹²⁸ is a method to predict droplet-driver promoting regions and proteins. The algorithm was trained on a dataset of drivers collected from different public databases, and the output is a per-residue probability of droplet formation. <https://fuzdrop.bio.unipd.it/predictor>

Section 6 - Low Complexity Regions (LCRs)

Overview:

Low Complexity Regions are protein or DNA sequences with a strong bias in the amino acid/nucleotide composition. These are usually divided into the following types: homorepeats, short tandem repeats, fuzzy regions and fused regions. The boundary of the definition of what is and what is not an LCR is represented on one hand by high complexity regions and on the other by long imperfect repeats ¹²⁹. LCRs represent both non-globular and globular structures. Non-globular LCRs often represent linkers, flanking sequences that are involved in specific types of binding or loops in transmembrane proteins. Globular LCRs are represented by well-known repetitive domains, like LRR, TPR, Armadillo ²⁴. LCRs are involved in many processes. In most cases known to date these represent mostly binding; nucleic acids, proteins, saccharides, ions, themselves in auto-aggregation processes. This last process, especially known in its specific form as liquid-liquid phase separation (LLPS), is crucial in forming subcellular structures like the nucleolus, P-body or stress granules ¹³⁰.

According to our analysis, 60% of proteins from the SWISSPROT database possess at least one LCR. Only 3% of prokaryotic sequences are LCRs, but this number hops to 15% for Eukaryotes (unpublished results). This abundance, only now better recognised as significant by the scientific community, stresses the importance of biased protein regions. They're not only important in wild type cell functions mentioned above, but also in disease. There are numerous mutations in LCR-encoding DNAs that can pose serious issues. One type of those is related to amyloid-related aggregation of KRT8 filament ¹³¹, another to repeat expansion, like in Huntington's disease, myotonic dystrophy, fragile X mental retardation syndrome or spinal and bulbar muscular atrophy ¹³².

Algorithms and tools to study LCRs

SEG ¹³³ was the first algorithm to detect LCRs within protein sequences. It calculates the number of amino acid occurrences for a given window, defined as a complexity state vector. For each vector the compositional complexity and the probability of occurrence can be computed,

and used to classify segments as low or high complexity regions based on a threshold value for sequence entropy. SEG is available as a part of NCBI BLAST+ package.

CAST ¹³⁴ is capable of detecting compositionally biased regions (CBRs) in protein sequences. The algorithm compares the query sequence against twenty homopolymers based on one of the 20 natural amino acid residue types. These homopolymers are used to create an artificial database consisting of 20 degenerate protein sequences of arbitrary length. The method is based on the idea that a homology search against such 'bias-database' will only return significant hits if the search query has regions with 'unusual' amino acid composition. The resulting matching 'homologue' immediately identifies the type and region of compositional bias. The CAST program is available on GitHub as a part of the [CGG toolkit](#) ¹³⁵ or via [PlaToLoCO web server interface](#) ¹³⁶.

fLPS ^{137,138} annotates CBRs by detecting both single- and multiple-residue biases and works through a process of probability minimization. In the first step fLPS creates contigs for each amino acid type from sequence windows that are biased according to a high bias probability threshold. Then, each contig is searched exhaustively for low probability subsequences (LPSs). A final list of single-residue LPSs is obtained by calculating the binomial P-values of the subsequences, sorting on increasing order of P-value, and gradually excluding overlapping entries with higher P-values. Finally, LPSs for different residue types are iteratively assessed for possible merger to produce as an output all single-residue and multiple-residue LPSs with information of their compositional biases in relation to the whole protein sequence. The tool is available to download from GitHub (<https://github.com/pmharrison/flps>) or via PlaToLoCO web server interface ¹³⁶.

SIMPLE ¹³⁹ was first developed to identify simple sequences in DNA, and later was extended to detect comparably cryptic sequences in amino acid sequences. The method runs three main types of analysis: (1) estimates the amount of simple sequence content in a sequence; (2) determines which short sequence motifs are significantly clustered; and (3) finds the location of simple sequences with significantly clustered motifs in the sequence. For each position in the sequence, the window of the defined length is scanned for repetitions of the motif starting at the central amino acid and a Simplicity Score (SS) is computed. The average SS over all positions in the sequence is calculated and divided by the average SS in a set of randomly generated sequences of the same length and composition as the test sequence. This gives a value of so-called relative simplicity factor (RSF). A RSF greater than 1 indicates significant overall simple sequence content in the sequence. The program is available upon request or via PlaToLoCO web server interface.

LCD-Composer is a method to detect low complexity regions (low complexity domains). Unlike other methods for LCRs detection that use mathematical definitions of sequence complexity or statistical enrichment of amino acids relative to whole-proteome frequencies, LCD-composer defines low complexity regions in proteins based on amino acid composition and linear dispersion of amino acids. The authors of the method argue that such an approach allows one

to take into account the physicochemical properties of LCDs. The method is available via [LCD-composer web server](#) ¹⁴⁰.

Other methods for LCRs detection include [XNU](#) ¹⁴¹, [CARD](#) ¹⁴², [GBA](#) ¹⁴³, [ScanCom](#) ¹⁴⁴, [SARP](#) ¹⁴⁵, [BIAS](#) ¹⁴⁶ and [Oj.py](#) ¹⁴⁷, [SubSequer](#) ¹⁴⁸, and [LPS-annotate](#) ¹⁴⁹. However, in many cases the implementation of those methods is not available any more.

Tandem repeats (TR) are specific types of low complexity regions characterized by a repetitive pattern of amino acids in a sequence. An extensive review of sequence based tools that can be used to predict tandem repeats in proteins was conducted in ¹⁵⁰. As in case of LCRs analysis, most of the methods are based on statistical properties of the sequences. To our best knowledge, there are only two methods based on a machine learning approach, which we present below:

T-REKS ¹⁵¹ is a method to identify tandem repeats, a specific type of LCRs. It is based on clustering of lengths between identical short strings by using an unsupervised *K*-means clustering algorithm. The authors propose an approach where the lengths between identical neighbouring short strings (protein fragments) are used as data points of the *K*-means algorithm to find potential lengths of the tandem repeats.

Tally 2.0 ¹⁵² is also focused on only one specific type of LCRs which are tandem repeats. Its second version is an improved version of the tandem repeat detection validator in protein sequences. It is based on a machine learning (ML) approach. The first version of this tool was developed to distinguish between TRs found both in sequence and in structure, and TRs only found in sequence, but not in the structure. The second version has been trained on a more comprehensive set of sequences and can be used more generally in the large-scale analyses as a uniform validator of TR detection. During the training phase the TR of a given region is presented as multiple sequence alignment (MSA) of its repeats. The MSAs are enriched with additional features based on Fourier Transform and physico-chemical characteristics of amino acids. The final model is trained using the Random Forest Classifier.

The MEME Suite ¹⁵³ is a motif based sequence analysis tool for studying sequence motifs in proteins, DNA and RNA. Motifs are short, conserved parts of sequences indicating their importance in maintaining specific protein function within the cell. The MEME is a suite of many different tools incorporating six different motif discovery algorithms, five motif search algorithms and additional tools for motif comparison, enrichment, annotation or prediction of regulatory links between regulatory elements. The MEME Suite does not include any specific tools directly related to LCR analyses, however since some motifs can also be characterized as having low complexity amino acid frequencies ¹⁵⁴, and therefore the MEME Suite results can also be used to characterize low complexity regions in protein sequences. For instance, both MEME and GLAM2 can be used for LCR motif discovery and Tomtom can be used to search one or more LCR motifs against a motif database (<https://meme-suite.org/meme/tools/meme>, <https://meme-suite.org/meme/tools/glam2>, <https://meme-suite.org/meme/tools/tomtom>).

The last example of a machine learning approach to analyse LCRs is to predict their functions, the [LCR-hound webserver](#)¹⁵⁵. It is a tool for identifying LCRs using a Shannon entropy and visualizing them on the protein sequence. LCR-hound also uses a neural network to predict a function of identified LCRs, based on their overall di-amino acid content. To train the network, the authors created four sets of LCRs, using as a base the functional annotation of their proteins that were further filtered by clustering of their amino acid content. For training and evaluation, LCRs were encoded as a vector of bigram frequencies of amino acids. The investigated groups represented the following functions: DNA-RNA-binding, metal-ion-binding, chaperone, and other.

Machine Learning is still in its infancy stages in the studies of LCRs. The number of tools that are using ML approaches for LCR detection is very limited as most of them are based on statistical properties of certain sequence features typically related to amino acid frequencies in comparison to the so-called high complexity regions. However, some ideas have been around for some time already. In particular, in the work¹⁵⁶ artificial sequences with known LCRs were used to train and evaluate an SVM classifier. For each position in the input sequence, the authors defined a set of features which have been used to calculate its complexity score for the set of artificially generated sequences. However, to the best of our knowledge, this method has never been implemented in any publicly available tool for LCRs analysis. Overall, we can clearly define advantages of ML over traditional statistical methods, especially in four areas: handling large and complex sets of data, automation and discovery of anomalies in the input (which is quite common in usually highly redundant biological data), efficiency and lastly generalisability, detection of patterns in processed information.

Section 7 - Transmembrane proteins (TM)

Membrane proteins constitute 20 to 30 % of all genes in eucaryotes and procaryotes¹⁵⁷. Transmembrane (TM) proteins are an important class of membrane proteins that span the membrane completely. TM proteins are involved in vital functions such as ion and water transport across the plasma membrane, protein secretion into the ER lumen and insertion into the ER membrane, and signal transduction. Also, more than half of FDA-approved small-molecule drugs target TM proteins¹⁵⁸. Experimental determination of TM protein structures is challenging, and currently, only about 5 % of protein structures in PDB are for TM proteins (about 11 000)^{159,160}. From the so far solved TM protein structures, we can conclude that most of them are purely α helical, while some TM proteins are rich with β sheets and form β barrels¹⁶¹.

One of the early computational tools that were developed to gain structural information about TM proteins was hydropathy plots¹⁶². For this, first, the hydrophobicity scales are created where the free energies of transfer for the side chains of the amino acids between various phases are obtained¹⁶²⁻¹⁶⁴. Then the size of a running window is chosen (typically between 7 and 13 amino acids), and the values from the hydrophobicity scale for corresponding amino acids are successively summed and plotted. Such a plot approximately shows which parts of the protein are embedded in the hydrophobic core of the membrane and which parts are facing the aqueous medium. This allows us to obtain the topology of TM proteins.

The development of hidden Markov model-based tools was the next important step in TM protein topology prediction starting in the late 90s and early 2000s^{157,165}. These techniques combine hydrophobicity, charge bias, helix lengths, amino acid distributions in various structural parts of the protein, and grammatical constraints into a single model. Already, the first such tools, HMMTOP¹⁶⁶ and TMHMM¹⁵⁷, had a single sequence topology prediction accuracy of about 78 %¹⁵⁷. SignalP is a tool for predicting signal peptides from the amino acid sequence and distinguishing between the signal peptide and TM helices^{167–170}. Signal peptides are 15 to 40 amino acid-long peptides in the N-terminus of newly synthesized proteins that are translocated by the translocon into the plasma membrane. The first version of SignalP was based on artificial neural networks with one hidden layer¹⁶⁷. In the second version, authors implemented hidden Markov model and currently the last version is based on protein language model¹⁷⁰. The development of the SignalP tool over time nicely illustrates on a small scale the development of methods used for making bioinformatics tools for TM proteins, namely, from simpler statistical methods to hidden Markov model¹⁶⁸, then deep neural networks¹⁶⁹ and protein language models¹⁷⁰. Another hidden Markov model-based tool, Phobius combines TM topology and signal peptide prediction in one tool¹⁷¹. Compared to TMHMM¹⁵⁷ and SignalP¹⁶⁸, Phobius noticeably reduced false classifications of TM helices and signal peptides¹⁷¹. The interactive protein feature visualization tool Protter¹⁷² <https://wlab.ethz.ch/protter/start/> can be used to analyse TM protein topology.

So far, the best tools described above for TM protein topology prediction are purely statistical and machine learning-based. However, from a biophysicist's point of view, this problem, in principle, should be possible to address using physicochemical principles of molecular interactions between amino acids, lipids, and water. Considering this in¹⁷³ authors developed two topology-prediction methods, TopPred^{AG} and SCAMPI, based on the biological hydrophobicity scale¹⁶⁴, which performed similarly well compared to the best statistical and machine learning-based tools of the time.

The development of artificial neural networks and later deep neural networks and transformers-based protein large language models strongly influenced ML tools for TM proteins. The artificial neural network-predicted residue scores combined with a hidden Markov model-based prediction algorithm was used in OCTOPUS for TM topology prediction that resulted in 94 % prediction accuracy¹⁷⁴. Philius, which is a TM topology and signal peptide prediction tool, uses dynamic Bayesian networks¹⁷⁵. Several of the above-discussed tools have been combined into consensus prediction web servers such as CCTOP¹⁷⁶ and TOPCONS¹⁷⁷.

Protein language model-based tools started to appear in the 2020s. For example, DeepTMHMM¹⁷⁸ and SignalP 6.0¹⁷⁰ are based on protein language models and are considerably better than their earlier versions discussed above (TMHMM and SignalP 1.0). Particularly, DeepTMHMM predicts topology for both α helical and β barrel TM proteins and even the presence of a signal peptide with very high accuracy¹⁷⁸.

Essentially, TM protein topology prediction is a step towards predicting protein structure from its sequence, which is the renowned protein folding problem that has been largely addressed by AlphaFold2⁶⁴. One of the important advantages of AlphaFold is that it not only predicts the

protein (and in the last version AlphaFold3¹⁷⁹ also nucleic acid and ligand) 3D structure but also provides predicted local distance difference test (pLDDT)¹⁸⁰ as a measure of model's confidence in its prediction. Although there are relatively small number of TM protein structures in PDB, AlphaFold2 generally performs well for TM protein structure prediction^{181,182}. The race for better models for protein (and other macromolecular) structure prediction is in full swing, and we see several foundation models being released recently, such as AlphaFold3¹⁷⁹, RoseTTAFold All-Atom¹⁸³, and Chai-1¹⁸⁴.

The protein design problem is an inverse of the protein folding problem. Here, we aim to generate an amino acid sequence that will fold into a specific 3D structure and perform a specific function. In recent years, the first α helical TM proteins have been de novo designed, containing two to four membrane-spanning helices¹⁸⁵ and then larger 12 to 16-helical pores formed by two concentric rings of helices¹⁸⁶. TM α helical proteins that specifically bind and regulate the erythropoietin receptor were also designed¹⁸⁷. TM β barrels have also been designed that do not have a homology to other known TM β barrel proteins¹⁸⁸. More recently, larger (10, 12, and 14 stranded) TM β barrel pores have been designed that can be used as small-molecule sensors¹⁸⁹. Recently, a curious study was conducted where researchers de novo designed soluble analogs of TM proteins¹⁹⁰. This is interesting since their topologies are not found in the soluble proteome. They succeeded and experimentally demonstrated the stability of such de novo designed proteins¹⁹⁰.

Lastly, we would like to mention UniTmp, a unified database for TM proteins containing annotated structural information of TM proteins¹⁶⁰.

Concluding Remarks:

Machine Learning is an active field for the study of protein sequences, structures and functions. However, most of the methods are focused and tailored to study globular proteins.

Here we have reviewed a large amount of machine learning based tools to analyse and study the properties of non-globular proteins of different types: Repeat proteins, aggregates, metamorphic proteins, disordered proteins, and proteins that undergo LLPS. Not only have we made a bibliographic review through each of the main classes but also made lists of computational tools specific for each of them. We have also created a GitHub repository (<https://github.com/nevenaciric/ML4NGP-WG3-report>) that serves as a unified resource where the general public can refer to find computational tools of their interest.

We expect this report to be of great interest for the community that is associated with our ML4NGP COST action and also to use it as the basis to write a review article which can serve as a white paper for our field.

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References:

1. Dill, K. A. & MacCallum, J. L. The Protein-Folding Problem, 50 Years On. *Science* **338**, 1042–1046 (2012).
2. Ling Kuan, S., G. Bergamini, F. R. & Weil, T. Functional protein nanostructures: a chemical toolbox. *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **47**, 9069–9105 (2018).
3. Jahn, T. R. & Radford, S. E. Folding versus aggregation: polypeptide conformations on competing pathways. *Arch. Biochem. Biophys.* **469**, 100–117 (2008).
4. Sawaya, M. R., Hughes, M. P., Rodriguez, J. A., Riek, R. & Eisenberg, D. S. The expanding amyloid family: Structure, stability, function, and pathogenesis. *Cell* **184**, 4857–4873 (2021).
5. Garcia-Pardo, J. & Ventura, S. Cryo-EM structures of functional and pathological amyloid ribonucleoprotein assemblies. *Trends Biochem. Sci.* (2023) doi:10.1016/j.tibs.2023.10.005.
6. Dobson, C. M., Knowles, T. P. J. & Vendruscolo, M. The Amyloid Phenomenon and Its Significance in Biology and Medicine. *Cold Spring Harb. Perspect. Biol.* **12**, a033878 (2020).
7. Dobson, C. M. Principles of protein folding, misfolding and aggregation. *Semin. Cell Dev. Biol.* **15**, 3–16 (2004).
8. Navarro, S. & Ventura, S. Computational methods to predict protein aggregation. *Curr. Opin. Struct. Biol.* **73**, 102343 (2022).
9. Pintado-Grima, C. *et al.* A Review of Fifteen Years Developing Computational Tools to Study Protein Aggregation. *Biophysica* **3**, 1–20 (2023).

10. Prabakaran, R., Rawat, P., Kumar, S. & Michael Gromiha, M. ANuPP: A Versatile Tool to Predict Aggregation Nucleating Regions in Peptides and Proteins. *J. Mol. Biol.* **433**, 166707 (2021).
11. Burdukiewicz, M. *et al.* Amyloidogenic motifs revealed by n-gram analysis. *Sci. Rep.* **7**, 12961 (2017).
12. Kim, C., Choi, J., Lee, S. J., Welsh, W. J. & Yoon, S. NetCSSP: web application for predicting chameleon sequences and amyloid fibril formation. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **37**, W469–W473 (2009).
13. Gasior, P. & Kotulska, M. FISH Amyloid – a new method for finding amyloidogenic segments in proteins based on site specific co-occurrence of aminoacids. *BMC Bioinformatics* **15**, 54 (2014).
14. Niu, M., Li, Y., Wang, C. & Han, K. RFAmyloid: A Web Server for Predicting Amyloid Proteins. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* **19**, 2071 (2018).
15. Keresztes, L. *et al.* The Budapest Amyloid Predictor and Its Applications. *Biomolecules* **11**, 500 (2021).
16. Wojciechowski, J. W. & Kotulska, M. PATH - Prediction of Amyloidogenicity by Threading and Machine Learning. *Sci. Rep.* **10**, 7721 (2020).
17. Sawaya, M. R. *et al.* Atomic structures of amyloid cross- β spines reveal varied steric zippers. *Nature* **447**, 453–457 (2007).
18. Louros, N., Orlando, G., De Vleeschouwer, M., Rousseau, F. & Schymkowitz, J. Structure-based machine-guided mapping of amyloid sequence space reveals uncharted sequence clusters with higher solubilities. *Nat. Commun.* **11**, 3314 (2020).
19. Orlando, G., Silva, A., Macedo-Ribeiro, S., Raimondi, D. & Vranken, W. Accurate prediction of protein beta-aggregation with generalized statistical potentials. *Bioinformatics* **36**, 2076–2081 (2020).
20. Li, Y., Zhang, Z., Teng, Z. & Liu, X. PredAmyl-MLP: Prediction of Amyloid Proteins Using

Multilayer Perceptron. *Comput. Math. Methods Med.* **2020**, 1–12 (2020).

21. Liaw, C., Tung, C.-W. & Ho, S.-Y. Prediction and Analysis of Antibody Amyloidogenesis from Sequences. *PLOS ONE* **8**, e53235 (2013).
22. Tian, J., Wu, N., Guo, J. & Fan, Y. Prediction of amyloid fibril-forming segments based on a support vector machine. *BMC Bioinformatics* **10**, S45 (2009).
23. Família, C., Dennison, S. R., Quintas, A. & Phoenix, D. A. Prediction of Peptide and Protein Propensity for Amyloid Formation. *PLOS ONE* **10**, e0134679 (2015).
24. Andrade, M. A., Perez-Iratxeta, C. & Ponting, C. P. Protein Repeats: Structures, Functions, and Evolution. *J. Struct. Biol.* **134**, 117–131 (2001).
25. Jorda, J., Baudrand, T. & Kajava, A. V. PRDB: Protein Repeat DataBase. *PROTEOMICS* **12**, 1333–1336 (2012).
26. Heringa, J. Detection of internal repeats: how common are they? *Curr. Opin. Struct. Biol.* **8**, 338–345 (1998).
27. Tompa, P. Intrinsically unstructured proteins evolve by repeat expansion. *BioEssays* **25**, 847–855 (2003).
28. Strand, M., Prolla, T. A., Liskay, R. M. & Petes, T. D. Destabilization of tracts of simple repetitive DNA in yeast by mutations affecting DNA mismatch repair. *Nature* **365**, 274–276 (1993).
29. Pâques, F., Leung, W.-Y. & Haber, J. E. Expansions and Contractions in a Tandem Repeat Induced by Double-Strand Break Repair. *Mol. Cell. Biol.* **18**, 2045–2054 (1998).
30. Kajava, A. V. Review: Proteins with Repeated Sequence—Structural Prediction and Modeling. *J. Struct. Biol.* **134**, 132–144 (2001).
31. Kajava, A. V. Tandem repeats in proteins: From sequence to structure. *J. Struct. Biol.* **179**, 279–288 (2012).
32. Di Domenico, T. *et al.* RepeatsDB: a database of tandem repeat protein structures. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **42**, D352–D357 (2014).

33. Paladin, L. *et al.* RepeatsDB in 2021: improved data and extended classification for protein tandem repeat structures. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **49**, D452–D457 (2020).
34. Espada, R. *et al.* Repeat proteins challenge the concept of structural domains. *Biochem. Soc. Trans.* **43**, 844–849 (2015).
35. Parra, R. G., Espada, R., Sánchez, I. E., Sippl, M. J. & Ferreiro, D. U. Detecting Repetitions and Periodicities in Proteins by Tiling the Structural Space. *J. Phys. Chem. B* **117**, 12887–12897 (2013).
36. Espada, R., Parra, R. G., Mora, T., Walczak, A. M. & Ferreiro, D. U. Capturing coevolutionary signals in repeat proteins. *BMC Bioinformatics* **16**, 207 (2015).
37. Mesdaghi, S., Price, R. M., Madine, J. & Rigden, D. J. Deep Learning-based structure modelling illuminates structure and function in uncharted regions of β -solenoid fold space. *J. Struct. Biol.* **215**, 108010 (2023).
38. Main, E. R., Lowe, A. R., Mochrie, S. G., Jackson, S. E. & Regan, L. A recurring theme in protein engineering: the design, stability and folding of repeat proteins. *Curr. Opin. Struct. Biol.* **15**, 464–471 (2005).
39. Boersma, Y. L. & Plückthun, A. DARPins and other repeat protein scaffolds: advances in engineering and applications. *Curr. Opin. Biotechnol.* **22**, 849–857 (2011).
40. Mosavi, L. K., Minor, D. L. & Peng, Z.-Y. Consensus-derived structural determinants of the ankyrin repeat motif. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* **99**, 16029–16034 (2002).
41. Binz, H. K., Stumpp, M. T., Forrer, P., Amstutz, P. & Plückthun, A. Designing Repeat Proteins: Well-expressed, Soluble and Stable Proteins from Combinatorial Libraries of Consensus Ankyrin Repeat Proteins. *J. Mol. Biol.* **332**, 489–503 (2003).
42. Binz, H. K. *et al.* High-affinity binders selected from designed ankyrin repeat protein libraries. *Nat. Biotechnol.* **22**, 575–582 (2004).
43. Aksel, T., Majumdar, A. & Barrick, D. The contribution of entropy, enthalpy, and hydrophobic desolvation to cooperativity in repeat-protein folding. *Struct. Lond. Engl.* **1993**

- 19**, 349–360 (2011).
44. Main, E. R. G., Xiong, Y., Cocco, M. J., D'Andrea, L. & Regan, L. Design of stable alpha-helical arrays from an idealized TPR motif. *Struct. Lond. Engl.* **1993** **11**, 497–508 (2003).
 45. Stumpp, M. T., Forrer, P., Binz, H. K. & Plückthun, A. Designing repeat proteins: modular leucine-rich repeat protein libraries based on the mammalian ribonuclease inhibitor family. *J. Mol. Biol.* **332**, 471–487 (2003).
 46. Baabur-Cohen, H., Dayalan, S., Shumacher, I., Cohen-Luria, R. & Ashkenasy, G. Artificial leucine rich repeats as new scaffolds for protein design. *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.* **21**, 2372–2375 (2011).
 47. Lee, S.-C. *et al.* Design of a binding scaffold based on variable lymphocyte receptors of jawless vertebrates by module engineering. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* **109**, 3299–3304 (2012).
 48. Parker, R., Mercedes-Camacho, A. & Grove, T. Z. Consensus design of a NOD receptor leucine rich repeat domain with binding affinity for a muramyl dipeptide, a bacterial cell wall fragment. *Protein Sci. Publ. Protein Soc.* **23**, 790–800 (2014).
 49. Urvoas, A. *et al.* Design, production and molecular structure of a new family of artificial alpha-helicoidal repeat proteins (α Rep) based on thermostable HEAT-like repeats. *J. Mol. Biol.* **404**, 307–327 (2010).
 50. Parmeggiani, F. *et al.* Designed Armadillo Repeat Proteins as General Peptide-Binding Scaffolds: Consensus Design and Computational Optimization of the Hydrophobic Core. *J. Mol. Biol.* **376**, 1282–1304 (2008).
 51. Nikkhah, M., Jawad-Alami, Z., Demydchuk, M., Ribbons, D. & Paoli, M. Engineering of beta-propeller protein scaffolds by multiple gene duplication and fusion of an idealized WD repeat. *Biomol. Eng.* **23**, 185–194 (2006).
 52. Parra, R. G., Espada, R., Verstraete, N. & Ferreira, D. U. Structural and Energetic Characterization of the Ankyrin Repeat Protein Family. *PLOS Comput. Biol.* **11**, e1004659

(2015).

53. Magliery, T. J. & Regan, L. Beyond consensus: statistical free energies reveal hidden interactions in the design of a TPR motif. *J. Mol. Biol.* **343**, 731–745 (2004).
54. Socolich, M. *et al.* Evolutionary information for specifying a protein fold. *Nature* **437**, 512–518 (2005).
55. Sullivan, B. J. *et al.* Stabilizing Proteins from Sequence Statistics: The Interplay of Conservation and Correlation in Triosephosphate Isomerase Stability. *J. Mol. Biol.* **420**, 384–399 (2012).
56. Simons, K. T., Kooperberg, C., Huang, E. & Baker, D. Assembly of protein tertiary structures from fragments with similar local sequences using simulated annealing and bayesian scoring functions¹¹Edited by F. E. Cohen. *J. Mol. Biol.* **268**, 209–225 (1997).
57. Huang, P.-S., Boyken, S. E. & Baker, D. The coming of age of de novo protein design. *Nature* **537**, 320–327 (2016).
58. Correnti, C. E. *et al.* Engineering and functionalization of large circular tandem repeat protein nanoparticles. *Nat. Struct. Mol. Biol.* **27**, 342–350 (2020).
59. Hallinan, J. P. *et al.* Design of functionalised circular tandem repeat proteins with longer repeat topologies and enhanced subunit contact surfaces. *Commun. Biol.* **4**, 1–14 (2021).
60. Doyle, L. A. *et al.* De novo design of knotted tandem repeat proteins. *Nat. Commun.* **14**, 6746 (2023).
61. Doyle, L. *et al.* Rational design of α -helical tandem repeat proteins with closed architectures. *Nature* **528**, 585–588 (2015).
62. Senior, A. W. *et al.* Improved protein structure prediction using potentials from deep learning. *Nature* **577**, 706–710 (2020).
63. Kryshtafovych, A., Schwede, T., Topf, M., Fidelis, K. & Moult, J. Critical assessment of methods of protein structure prediction (CASP)—Round XIII. *Proteins Struct. Funct. Bioinforma.* **87**, 1011–1020 (2019).

64. Jumper, J. *et al.* Highly accurate protein structure prediction with AlphaFold. *Nature* **596**, 583–589 (2021).
65. Rives, A. *et al.* Biological structure and function emerge from scaling unsupervised learning to 250 million protein sequences. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* **118**, e2016239118 (2021).
66. Elnaggar, A. *et al.* ProtTrans: Toward Understanding the Language of Life Through Self-Supervised Learning. *IEEE Trans. Pattern Anal. Mach. Intell.* **44**, 7112–7127 (2022).
67. Ferruz, N. *et al.* From sequence to function through structure: Deep learning for protein design. *Comput. Struct. Biotechnol. J.* **21**, 238–250 (2022).
68. Romero-Romero, S., Lindner, S. & Ferruz, N. Exploring the Protein Sequence Space with Global Generative Models. *Cold Spring Harb. Perspect. Biol.* **15**, a041471 (2023).
69. Dauparas, J. *et al.* Robust deep learning based protein sequence design using ProteinMPNN. *Science* **378**, 49–56 (2022).
70. Anishchenko, I. *et al.* De novo protein design by deep network hallucination. *Nature* **600**, 547–552 (2021).
71. Wicky, B. I. M. *et al.* Hallucinating symmetric protein assemblies. *Science* **378**, 56–61 (2022).
72. An, L. *et al.* Hallucination of closed repeat proteins containing central pockets. *Nat. Struct. Mol. Biol.* **30**, 1755–1760 (2023).
73. Tischer, D. *et al.* Design of proteins presenting discontinuous functional sites using deep learning. 2020.11.29.402743 Preprint at <https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.11.29.402743> (2020).
74. Wang, J. *et al.* Scaffolding protein functional sites using deep learning. *Science* **377**, 387–394 (2022).
75. Frank, C. *et al.* Efficient and scalable de novo protein design using a relaxed sequence space. 2023.02.24.529906 Preprint at <https://doi.org/10.1101/2023.02.24.529906> (2023).
76. Sohl-Dickstein, J., Weiss, E., Maheswaranathan, N. & Ganguli, S. Deep Unsupervised

- Learning using Nonequilibrium Thermodynamics. in *Proceedings of the 32nd International Conference on Machine Learning* 2256–2265 (PMLR, 2015).
77. Song, Y. & Ermon, S. Generative Modeling by Estimating Gradients of the Data Distribution. in *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems* vol. 32 (Curran Associates, Inc., 2019).
 78. Ho, J., Jain, A. & Abbeel, P. Denoising Diffusion Probabilistic Models. Preprint at <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2006.11239> (2020).
 79. Anand, N. & Achim, T. Protein Structure and Sequence Generation with Equivariant Denoising Diffusion Probabilistic Models. Preprint at <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2205.15019> (2022).
 80. Watson, J. L. *et al.* De novo design of protein structure and function with RFdiffusion. *Nature* **620**, 1089–1100 (2023).
 81. Wu, R. *et al.* High-resolution de novo structure prediction from primary sequence. 2022.07.21.500999 Preprint at <https://doi.org/10.1101/2022.07.21.500999> (2022).
 82. Lin, Z. *et al.* Evolutionary-scale prediction of atomic-level protein structure with a language model. *Science* **379**, 1123–1130 (2023).
 83. Huang, P.-S. *et al.* High thermodynamic stability of parametrically designed helical bundles. *Science* **346**, 481–485 (2014).
 84. Voet, A. R. D. *et al.* Computational design of a self-assembling symmetrical β -propeller protein. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* **111**, 15102–15107 (2014).
 85. Rämisch, S., Weininger, U., Martinsson, J., Akke, M. & André, I. Computational design of a leucine-rich repeat protein with a predefined geometry. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* **111**, 17875–17880 (2014).
 86. Parmeggiani, F. *et al.* A General Computational Approach for Repeat Protein Design. *J. Mol. Biol.* **427**, 563–575 (2015).
 87. Park, K. *et al.* Control of repeat protein curvature by computational protein design. *Nat.*

- Struct. Mol. Biol.* **22**, 167–174 (2015).
88. Brunette, T. J. *et al.* Exploring the repeat protein universe through computational protein design. *Nature* **528**, 580–584 (2015).
 89. Huang, P.-S. *et al.* De novo design of a four-fold symmetric TIM-barrel protein with atomic-level accuracy. *Nat. Chem. Biol.* **12**, 29–34 (2016).
 90. Chakravarty, D. & Porter, L. L. AlphaFold2 fails to predict protein fold switching. *Protein Sci. Publ. Protein Soc.* **31**, e4353 (2022).
 91. Schafer, J. W. & Porter, L. L. Evolutionary selection of proteins with two folds. *Nat. Commun.* **14**, 5478 (2023).
 92. Balakrishnan, S., Kamisetty, H., Carbonell, J. G., Lee, S.-I. & Langmead, C. J. Learning generative models for protein fold families. *Proteins Struct. Funct. Bioinforma.* **79**, 1061–1078 (2011).
 93. Kamisetty, H., Ovchinnikov, S. & Baker, D. Assessing the utility of coevolution-based residue–residue contact predictions in a sequence- and structure-rich era. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* **110**, 15674–15679 (2013).
 94. Rao, R. M. *et al.* MSA Transformer. in *Proceedings of the 38th International Conference on Machine Learning* 8844–8856 (PMLR, 2021).
 95. Bryant, P. Structure prediction of alternative protein conformations. 2023.09.25.559256 Preprint at <https://doi.org/10.1101/2023.09.25.559256> (2023).
 96. Wayment-Steele, H. K., Ovchinnikov, S., Colwell, L. & Kern, D. Prediction of multiple conformational states by combining sequence clustering with AlphaFold2. 2022.10.17.512570 Preprint at <https://doi.org/10.1101/2022.10.17.512570> (2022).
 97. Brotzakis, Z. F., Zhang, S. & Vendruscolo, M. AlphaFold Prediction of Structural Ensembles of Disordered Proteins. 2023.01.19.524720 Preprint at <https://doi.org/10.1101/2023.01.19.524720> (2023).
 98. Ganne, A., Balasubramaniam, M., Ayyadevara, S. & Shmookler Reis, R. J.

- Machine-learning analysis of intrinsically disordered proteins identifies key factors that contribute to neurodegeneration-related aggregation. *Front. Aging Neurosci.* **14**, 938117 (2022).
99. Tesei, G. *et al.* Conformational ensembles of the human intrinsically disordered proteome: Bridging chain compaction with function and sequence conservation. 2023.05.08.539815 Preprint at <https://doi.org/10.1101/2023.05.08.539815> (2023).
 100. Deng, X., Eickholt, J. & Cheng, J. A comprehensive overview of computational protein disorder prediction methods. *Mol. Biosyst.* **8**, 114–121 (2012).
 101. Necci, M., Piovesan, D. & Tosatto, S. C. E. Critical assessment of protein intrinsic disorder prediction. *Nat. Methods* **18**, 472–481 (2021).
 102. Liu, Y., Wang, X. & Liu, B. A comprehensive review and comparison of existing computational methods for intrinsically disordered protein and region prediction. *Brief. Bioinform.* **20**, 330–346 (2019).
 103. Wang, S., Ma, J. & Xu, J. AUCpreD: proteome-level protein disorder prediction by AUC-maximized deep convolutional neural fields. *Bioinforma. Oxf. Engl.* **32**, i672–i679 (2016).
 104. Hu, G. *et al.* fIDPnn: Accurate intrinsic disorder prediction with putative propensities of disorder functions. *Nat. Commun.* **12**, 4438 (2021).
 105. Orlando, G., Raimondi, D., Codicè, F., Tabaro, F. & Vranken, W. Prediction of Disordered Regions in Proteins with Recurrent Neural Networks and Protein Dynamics. *J. Mol. Biol.* **434**, 167579 (2022).
 106. Deng, X., Eickholt, J. & Cheng, J. PreDisorder: ab initio sequence-based prediction of protein disordered regions. *BMC Bioinformatics* **10**, 436 (2009).
 107. Mirabello, C. & Wallner, B. rawMSA: End-to-end Deep Learning using raw Multiple Sequence Alignments. *PLoS ONE* **14**, e0220182 (2019).
 108. Hanson, J., Yang, Y., Paliwal, K. & Zhou, Y. Improving protein disorder prediction by deep

- bidirectional long short-term memory recurrent neural networks. *Bioinforma. Oxf. Engl.* **33**, 685–692 (2017).
109. Hanson, J., Paliwal, K. K., Litfin, T. & Zhou, Y. SPOT-Disorder2: Improved Protein Intrinsic Disorder Prediction by Ensembled Deep Learning. *Genomics Proteomics Bioinformatics* **17**, 645–656 (2019).
110. Hanson, J., Paliwal, K. & Zhou, Y. Accurate Single-Sequence Prediction of Protein Intrinsic Disorder by an Ensemble of Deep Recurrent and Convolutional Architectures. *J. Chem. Inf. Model.* **58**, 2369–2376 (2018).
111. Jones, D. T. & Cozzetto, D. DISOPRED3: precise disordered region predictions with annotated protein-binding activity. *Bioinformatics* **31**, 857–863 (2015).
112. Ward, J. J., Sodhi, J. S., McGuffin, L. J., Buxton, B. F. & Jones, D. T. Prediction and Functional Analysis of Native Disorder in Proteins from the Three Kingdoms of Life. *J. Mol. Biol.* **337**, 635–645 (2004).
113. Jones, D. T. & Ward, J. J. Prediction of disordered regions in proteins from position specific score matrices. *Proteins Struct. Funct. Bioinforma.* **53**, 573–578 (2003).
114. Linding, R. *et al.* Protein Disorder Prediction: Implications for Structural Proteomics. *Structure* **11**, 1453–1459 (2003).
115. Meng, F. & Kurgan, L. DFLpred: High-throughput prediction of disordered flexible linker regions in protein sequences. *Bioinformatics* **32**, i341–i350 (2016).
116. Kawashima, S. *et al.* AAindex: amino acid index database, progress report 2008. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **36**, D202–D205 (2008).
117. Dosztányi, Z., Csizmók, V., Tompa, P. & Simon, I. The Pairwise Energy Content Estimated from Amino Acid Composition Discriminates between Folded and Intrinsically Unstructured Proteins. *J. Mol. Biol.* **347**, 827–839 (2005).
118. Iqbal, S. & Hoque, M. T. Estimation of Position Specific Energy as a Feature of Protein Residues from Sequence Alone for Structural Classification. *PLoS ONE* **11**, e0161452

- (2016).
119. Iqbal, S., Mishra, A. & Hoque, M. T. Improved prediction of accessible surface area results in efficient energy function application. *J. Theor. Biol.* **380**, 380–391 (2015).
 120. Faraggi, E., Zhang, T., Yang, Y., Kurgan, L. & Zhou, Y. SPINE X: Improving protein secondary structure prediction by multi-step learning coupled with prediction of solvent accessible surface area and backbone torsion angles. *J. Comput. Chem.* **33**, 259–267 (2012).
 121. Necci, M., Piovesan, D., Dosztányi, Z. & Tosatto, S. C. E. MobiDB-lite: fast and highly specific consensus prediction of intrinsic disorder in proteins. *Bioinformatics* **33**, 1402–1404 (2017).
 122. Orlando, G. *et al.* Computational identification of prion-like RNA-binding proteins that form liquid phase-separated condensates. *Bioinformatics* **35**, 4617–4623 (2019).
 123. Lancaster, A. K., Nutter-Upham, A., Lindquist, S. & King, O. D. PLAAC: a web and command-line application to identify proteins with prion-like amino acid composition. *Bioinformatics* **30**, 2501–2502 (2014).
 124. Vernon, R. M. *et al.* Pi-Pi contacts are an overlooked protein feature relevant to phase separation. *eLife* **7**, e31486.
 125. Bolognesi, B. *et al.* A Concentration-Dependent Liquid Phase Separation Can Cause Toxicity upon Increased Protein Expression. *Cell Rep.* **16**, 222–231 (2016).
 126. Sun, T. *et al.* Prediction of liquid-liquid phase separation proteins using machine learning. 842336 Preprint at <https://doi.org/10.1101/842336> (2019).
 127. Mierlo, G. van *et al.* Predicting protein condensate formation using machine learning. *Cell Rep.* **34**, (2021).
 128. Hardenberg, M., Horvath, A., Ambrus, V., Fuxreiter, M. & Vendruscolo, M. Widespread occurrence of the droplet state of proteins in the human proteome. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* **117**, 33254–33262 (2020).

129. Mier, P. *et al.* Disentangling the complexity of low complexity proteins. *Brief. Bioinform.* **21**, 458–472 (2020).
130. Zhang, H. *et al.* Liquid-liquid phase separation in biology: mechanisms, physiological functions and human diseases. *Sci. China Life Sci.* **63**, 953–985 (2020).
131. Murray, K. A. *et al.* Identifying amyloid-related diseases by mapping mutations in low-complexity protein domains to pathologies. *Nat. Struct. Mol. Biol.* **29**, 529–536 (2022).
132. La Spada, A. R. & Taylor, J. P. Repeat expansion disease: progress and puzzles in disease pathogenesis. *Nat. Rev. Genet.* **11**, 247–258 (2010).
133. Wootton, J. C. & Federhen, S. Statistics of local complexity in amino acid sequences and sequence databases. *Comput. Chem.* **17**, 149–163 (1993).
134. Promponas, V. J. *et al.* CAST: an iterative algorithm for the complexity analysis of sequence tracts. *Bioinformatics* **16**, 915–922 (2000).
135. Vasileiou, D. *et al.* CGG toolkit: Software components for computational genomics. *PLOS Comput. Biol.* **19**, e1011498 (2023).
136. Jarnot, P. *et al.* PlaToLoCo: the first web meta-server for visualization and annotation of low complexity regions in proteins. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **48**, W77–W84 (2020).
137. Harrison, P. M. fLPS: Fast discovery of compositional biases for the protein universe. *BMC Bioinformatics* **18**, 476 (2017).
138. Harrison, P. M. Optimizing strategy for the discovery of compositionally-biased or low-complexity regions in proteins. *Sci. Rep.* **14**, 680 (2024).
139. Albà, M. M., Laskowski, R. A. & Hancock, J. M. Detecting cryptically simple protein sequences using the SIMPLE algorithm. *Bioinformatics* **18**, 672–678 (2002).
140. Cascarina, S. M. & Ross, E. D. The LCD-Composer webserver: high-specificity identification and functional analysis of low-complexity domains in proteins. *Bioinformatics* **38**, 5446–5448 (2022).
141. Claverie, J.-M. & States, D. J. Information enhancement methods for large scale sequence

- analysis. *Comput. Chem.* **17**, 191–201 (1993).
142. Shin, S. W. & Kim, S. M. A new algorithm for detecting low-complexity regions in protein sequences. *Bioinformatics* **21**, 160–170 (2005).
143. Bandyopadhyay, N. & Kahveci, T. GBA manager: an online tool for querying low-complexity regions in proteins. *J. Comput. Biol. J. Comput. Mol. Cell Biol.* **17**, 73–77 (2010).
144. Nandi, T. *et al.* A Novel Complexity Measure for Comparative Analysis of Protein Sequences from Complete Genomes. *J. Biomol. Struct. Dyn.* **20**, 657–667 (2003).
145. Antonets, K. S. & Nizhnikov, A. A. SARP: A Novel Algorithm to Assess Compositional Biases in Protein Sequences. *Evol. Bioinforma.* **9**, EBO.S12299 (2013).
146. Kuznetsov, I. B. & Hwang, S. A novel sensitive method for the detection of user-defined compositional bias in biological sequences. *Bioinformatics* **22**, 1055–1063 (2006).
147. Wise, M. J. Oj.py: a software tool for low complexity proteins and protein domains. *Bioinformatics* **17**, S288–S295 (2001).
148. He, D. & Parkinson, J. SubSeqer: a graph-based approach for the detection and identification of repetitive elements in low-complexity sequences. *Bioinformatics* **24**, 1016–1017 (2008).
149. Harbi, D., Kumar, M. & Harrison, P. M. LPS-annotate: complete annotation of compositionally biased regions in the protein knowledgebase. *Database* **2011**, baq031–baq031 (2011).
150. Pellegrini, M. Tandem Repeats in Proteins: Prediction Algorithms and Biological Role. *Front. Bioeng. Biotechnol.* **3**, (2015).
151. Jorda, J. & Kajava, A. V. T-REKS: identification of Tandem REpeats in sequences with a K-meanS based algorithm. *Bioinformatics* **25**, 2632–2638 (2009).
152. Perovic, V. *et al.* Tally-2.0: upgraded validator of tandem repeat detection in protein sequences. *Bioinformatics* **36**, 3260–3262 (2020).

153. Bailey, T. L., Johnson, J., Grant, C. E. & Noble, W. S. The MEME Suite. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **43**, W39–W49 (2015).
154. Krystkowiak, I. & Davey, N. E. SLiMSearch: a framework for proteome-wide discovery and annotation of functional modules in intrinsically disordered regions. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **45**, W464–W469 (2017).
155. Ntountoumi, C. *et al.* Low complexity regions in the proteins of prokaryotes perform important functional roles and are highly conserved. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **47**, 9998–10009 (2019).
156. Barber, C. A. & Oehmen, C. S. An efficient machine learning approach to low-complexity filtering in biological sequences. in *2012 IEEE Symposium on Computational Intelligence in Bioinformatics and Computational Biology (CIBCB)* 237–243 (IEEE, San Diego, CA, 2012). doi:10.1109/CIBCB.2012.6217236.
157. Krogh, A., Larsson, B., von Heijne, G. & Sonnhammer, E. L. Predicting transmembrane protein topology with a hidden Markov model: application to complete genomes. *J. Mol. Biol.* **305**, 567–580 (2001).
158. Santos, R. *et al.* A comprehensive map of molecular drug targets. *Nat. Rev. Drug Discov.* **16**, 19–34 (2017).
159. Kozma, D., Simon, I. & Tusnády, G. E. PDBTM: Protein Data Bank of transmembrane proteins after 8 years. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **41**, D524–D529 (2013).
160. Dobson, L. *et al.* UniTmp: unified resources for transmembrane proteins. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **52**, D572–D578 (2024).
161. *Cell Boundaries : How Membranes and Their Proteins Work.* (Garland Science, 2021). doi:10.1201/9780429341328.
162. Kyte, J. & Doolittle, R. F. A simple method for displaying the hydropathic character of a protein. *J. Mol. Biol.* **157**, 105–132 (1982).
163. Wimley, W. C. & White, S. H. Experimentally determined hydrophobicity scale for proteins

- at membrane interfaces. *Nat. Struct. Biol.* **3**, 842–848 (1996).
164. Hessa, T. *et al.* Recognition of transmembrane helices by the endoplasmic reticulum translocon. *Nature* **433**, 377–381 (2005).
 165. Tusnády, G. E. & Simon, I. Principles governing amino acid composition of integral membrane proteins: application to topology prediction. *J. Mol. Biol.* **283**, 489–506 (1998).
 166. Tusnády, G. E. & Simon, I. The HMMTOP transmembrane topology prediction server. *Bioinforma. Oxf. Engl.* **17**, 849–850 (2001).
 167. Nielsen, H., Engelbrecht, J., Brunak, S. & von Heijne, G. Identification of prokaryotic and eukaryotic signal peptides and prediction of their cleavage sites. *Protein Eng.* **10**, 1–6 (1997).
 168. Nielsen, H. & Krogh, A. Prediction of signal peptides and signal anchors by a hidden Markov model. *Proc. Int. Conf. Intell. Syst. Mol. Biol.* **6**, 122–130 (1998).
 169. Almagro Armenteros, J. J. *et al.* SignalP 5.0 improves signal peptide predictions using deep neural networks. *Nat. Biotechnol.* **37**, 420–423 (2019).
 170. Teufel, F. *et al.* SignalP 6.0 predicts all five types of signal peptides using protein language models. *Nat. Biotechnol.* **40**, 1023–1025 (2022).
 171. Käll, L., Krogh, A. & Sonnhammer, E. L. L. A combined transmembrane topology and signal peptide prediction method. *J. Mol. Biol.* **338**, 1027–1036 (2004).
 172. Omasits, U., Ahrens, C. H., Müller, S. & Wollscheid, B. Protter: interactive protein feature visualization and integration with experimental proteomic data. *Bioinforma. Oxf. Engl.* **30**, 884–886 (2014).
 173. Bernsel, A. *et al.* Prediction of membrane-protein topology from first principles. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* **105**, 7177–7181 (2008).
 174. Viklund, H. & Elofsson, A. OCTOPUS: improving topology prediction by two-track ANN-based preference scores and an extended topological grammar. *Bioinformatics* **24**, 1662–1668 (2008).

175. Reynolds, S. M., Käll, L., Riffle, M. E., Bilmes, J. A. & Noble, W. S. Transmembrane topology and signal peptide prediction using dynamic bayesian networks. *PLoS Comput. Biol.* **4**, e1000213 (2008).
176. Dobson, L., Reményi, I. & Tusnády, G. E. CCTOP: a Consensus Constrained TOPology prediction web server. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **43**, W408-412 (2015).
177. Tsigos, K. D., Peters, C., Shu, N., Käll, L. & Elofsson, A. The TOPCONS web server for consensus prediction of membrane protein topology and signal peptides. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **43**, W401-407 (2015).
178. Hallgren, J. *et al.* DeepTMHMM predicts alpha and beta transmembrane proteins using deep neural networks. 2022.04.08.487609 Preprint at <https://doi.org/10.1101/2022.04.08.487609> (2022).
179. Abramson, J. *et al.* Accurate structure prediction of biomolecular interactions with AlphaFold 3. *Nature* **630**, 493–500 (2024).
180. Mariani, V., Biasini, M., Barbato, A. & Schwede, T. IDDT: a local superposition-free score for comparing protein structures and models using distance difference tests. *Bioinforma. Oxf. Engl.* **29**, 2722–2728 (2013).
181. Hegedűs, T., Geisler, M., Lukács, G. L. & Farkas, B. Ins and outs of AlphaFold2 transmembrane protein structure predictions. *Cell. Mol. Life Sci. CMLS* **79**, 73 (2022).
182. Dobson, L. *et al.* TmAlphaFold database: membrane localization and evaluation of AlphaFold2 predicted alpha-helical transmembrane protein structures. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **51**, D517–D522 (2023).
183. Krishna, R. *et al.* Generalized biomolecular modeling and design with RoseTTAFold All-Atom. *Science* **384**, ead12528 (2024).
184. Discovery, C. *et al.* Chai-1: Decoding the molecular interactions of life. 2024.10.10.615955 Preprint at <https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.10.10.615955> (2024).
185. Lu, P. *et al.* Accurate computational design of multipass transmembrane proteins. *Science*

- 359**, 1042–1046 (2018).
186. Xu, C. *et al.* Computational design of transmembrane pores. *Nature* **585**, 129–134 (2020).
187. Mravic, M. *et al.* De novo-designed transmembrane proteins bind and regulate a cytokine receptor. *Nat. Chem. Biol.* **20**, 751–760 (2024).
188. Vorobieva, A. A. *et al.* De novo design of transmembrane β barrels. *Science* **371**, eabc8182 (2021).
189. Berhanu, S. *et al.* Sculpting conducting nanopore size and shape through de novo protein design. *Science* **385**, 282–288 (2024).
190. Goverde, C. A. *et al.* Computational design of soluble and functional membrane protein analogues. *Nature* **631**, 449–458 (2024).